

Statistical Analysis and Predictive Learning of Mechanical Parameters for TiO₂ Filled GFRP Composite

Authors : S.SrinivasaMoorthy and K.Manonmani

Abstract : The new, polymer composites consisting of e-glass fiber reinforcement with titanium oxide filler in the double bonded unsaturated polyester resin matrix were made. The glass fiber and titanium oxide reinforcement composites were made in three different fiber lengths (3 cm, 5cm and 7 cm), filler content (2 wt%, 4 wt% and 6 wt%) and fiber content (20 wt%, 40 wt% and 60 wt%). 27 different compositions were fabricated and a sequence of experiments were carried out to determine tensile strength and impact strength. The vital influencing factors fiber length, fiber content and filler content were chosen as 3 factors in 3 levels of Taguchi's L9 orthogonal array. The influences of parameters were determined for tensile strength and impact strength by Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and S/N ratio. Using Artificial Neural Network (ANN) an expert system was devised to predict the properties of hybrid reinforcement GFRP composites. The predict models were experimentally proved with the maximum coincidence.

Keywords : Analysis of variance (ANOVA), Artificial neural network (ANN), Polymer composites, Taguchi's orthogonal array.

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